

Adoption of Sports Law Principles in Esports: The need for a more comprehensive governance model in Esports to protect stakeholders.

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Abstract

The esports industry has grown from strength to strength since the turn of the century having grown in viewership year on year and is predicted to have a larger viewership than every US professional sports league other than the NFL in 2021. As a result, more the professionalism and scrutiny of esports has grown with a number of organisations created to govern the ecosystem. The project used systematic review with thematic analysis to examine existing and past esports governance models, cases and events alongside a sports comparison. This was to help understand how effective governance has been in esports and if it could be improved to better protect stakeholders.

Sports is still developing its governance with recent corruption within FIFA and the IOC but has underlined transparency, financial integrity and accountability as principles to improve its governance; these are considerations that esports should follow. Past and existing esports governing organisations have failed or lack authority in esports due to control of publisher intellectual property rights ensuring they have full control of the game titles. Global esports governing organisations have also been created frequently and promotes confusion among stakeholders over their authority and the aims for the industry. Since the creation of WESA and ESIC, it has seen improvements in governing esports with the protection of the integrity within competition and the operations of leagues and teams. However, they are missing principles laid out by sports failures leaving stakeholders worried about conflict of interest over certain decisions. This dissertation will consider the need for better governance in esports, and if it should be controlled by publishers with the support of existing organisations or the formation of national governing bodies as grassroots competition continues to grow.

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Abbreviations

COD: Call of Duty

CS:GO: Counter-Strike Global Offensive

DCMS: Department of Digital, Culture, Media and Sport

EEF: Europe Esports Federation

ESIC: Esports Integrity Commission

GEF: Global Esports Federation

GEO: Global Esports Organisation

IEA: International Esports Association

leEF: International Esports Federation

IOC: International Olympic Committee

ISF: International Sports Federations

KeSPA: Korea Esports Association

LOL: League of Legends

NGB: National Governing Body

UKeSA: United Kingdom Esports Association

WESA: World Esports Association

Chapter 1: Introduction and Research Gap

1.1 Introduction

Due to the rapid growth of esports over the last 10 to 20 years, it has seen change within the landscape of competitive games and regulation of competitions. It was important to generate a list of keywords to help identify which literature fits under the esports umbrella. Following this technique from Creswell and Creswell (2018), a list was developed including words such as esports, Competitive Gaming, Cyber Law and Virtual Competition. Within the journal article by Reitman, *et al.*, (2019), it highlighted that there was a lack of research being conducted in seven key areas within esports (Media Studies, Informatics, Business, Sport Science, Sociology, Law and Cognitive Science) with only 150 publications across all seven areas. It stated that “Esports research’s nascency means there are still fundamental questions about how the field is unfolding” (Reitman, *et al.*, 2019, p.49). This is a worrying trend developing around the research of esports considering that it is projected to be an industry worth billions of dollars by 2023 (Soto Reyes, 2019).

With the continued classification of esports as a sport around the world, it would ultimately bring more litigation from and against a number of stakeholders in the industry (Kaburakis, *et al.*, 2017). Within existing literature, there has been an evaluation of how esports governance and ecosystem could be subject to litigation. It is only until recently that more legal cases such as McLeod v. Valve Corporation (2016) and Okkonen v. Valve GmbH (2020), have highlighted the rapid growth of litigation within esports. The purpose of this paper is to review the current governance that occurs in esports and to understand if a system could be developed to protect stakeholders.

1.2 The Existing Landscape of Esports Governance

In recent years, there has been a large injection of funds within esports and has seen academics evaluate if the current governance models are able to support stakeholders. Rogers (2019) highlights that ‘Governance also begs the question of how much involvement if any, lawmakers should have’. Research on this issue weights up both self-regulation, global governances and government intervention. Further research needs to document how each governance model would impact stakeholders within the esports ecosystem from the team, tournament organisation, players and

fans. Within Rogers (2019) it gives an evaluation of the current landscape of the esports scene in the context of member associations and what publishers do in enforcing decisions. The research, however, lacks any consideration of lawmaker influence or government intervention.

Research in the growth of esports looks at the first wave of litigation against publishers and the impact on the ability to regulate. The research conducted by Holden, *et al* (2017) uses the systematic review to identify a range of cases that have had an integral impact on gambling and doping within esports. The research also looked at the impact of national governance had on both the issue of gambling and doping, by comparing western and eastern culture in esports through the UK Gambling Commission and the Korean Esports Association. This identified that eastern countries had more impact from government influence on the governance of esports compared to western culture. This research highlighted that governance within eastern countries were more strict with gambling and corruption within esports compared to western countries.

1.3 The Existing and Potential Issues Facing Esports Governance

As early as 2017 during the steep growth of esports, research looked at the potential litigation that esports could face in line with what was learnt in the early commercialisation of sport. In research conducted by Kaburakis, *et al* (2017), it gives a more in-depth look at the type of statutes within the USA that could influence esports if it was considered a “entertainment activity” compared to a sport. It highlights what statutes could have a significant impact on the way esports is currently run, such as the Illegal Gambling Business Act (2006) and Bribery in Sporting Contests Act (1964). A key discovery made was that regulation of certain activities such as the operation of agents within college esports is allowed under “entertainment activity”, but if esports was considered a sport by the government it was be classed as illegal. It, however, does not follow up in what way self-regulation could be involved in ensuring better protection of younger players. The research by Karburakis, *et al* (2017), gives a good understanding to the question asked in Rogers (2019), that potential litigation issues would arise from government intervention, but does not give theories or ideas of how this could be tackled by publishers.

Future research should look more into the issues that external governing bodies would

face when regulating esports titles. In Miroff (2019) the research does not focus on esports governance and contributes to the knowledge surrounding why self-regulation is important within esports. The article looks at the rights that publishers have under copyright and antitrust laws. 'Publishers control esports markets through their monopoly on the IP to which all downstream entities must have access in order to compete' this highlights the total control that publishers have over their game and also uses the case of *KeSPA v Blizzard* (2010) to illustrate the strength of this claim. This research gives a clear and transparent view that the publisher has ultimate control. The research however leaves a gap in knowledge to whether self-regulation and executive backed governance could be achieved due to Intellectual rights held by publishers.

1.4 Sport Governance vs Esports Governance

With a number of comparisons identified between esports and sports research changed direction to look at what esports could gain from looking at sport governance models. One of the earliest works to look at the comparison of sport and esports in relation to the way rules and the culture of each differ was within Chao (2017). Chao highlights that there are significantly more stakeholders that have a say within the esports industry ranging from publishers to different organisers and states this is significantly different to sports that would cause issues over what direction governance should take. The research gives a clear understanding of issues of anti-competitive practices that are potentially a large issue in relation to franchised monopolies within esports compared to franchise models within US sport. While the article looks at more US laws and sports it would benefit the research if it looked at EU competition laws within the sport and how these could potentially affect esports in the future. Research in this field would allow an addition to knowledge and understanding of litigation of broadcasting monopolies and player contracts within esports under EU law. Due to the date of the article and the growth of esports, it does not research the effect of the new British Esports Association (BEA) and World Esports Association (WESA) on the landscape of esports governance.

The research gives a gap for further research on the topic of how publishers could self-regulate which is conducted by Martinelli (2019). Within the research conducted by Martinelli (2019), it looks at the current governance models in place within the

esports ecosystem, in regard to WESA, ESIC, WeSC and the BEA. Within the research, it identifies what each of these bodies are and what they aim to achieve. It does evaluate the cases and events that these bodies have been subjected to in recent times as well as why some are not seen as legitimate bodies to regulate esports. The conclusion of the research highlights “a significant regulatory problem within esports, there needs to be one organization that oversees the industry” (Martinelli, 2019). It then proceeds to recommend that it should follow a similar model to that of FIFA in which it handles its regulations and the benefit of being subject to swiss law. The research adds to the knowledge and view of why self-regulation would be a positive thing within esports that was a previous gap within past research of Rogers (2019) and Kaburakis (2017). The critique of this research and findings is that it conflicts with the findings of Miroff (2019), in which publishers have control over the direction of the game. Miroff (2019) highlights that a unified body between publishers may not be possible as there is existing competition as they try to achieve higher viewership and players bases within their respective esports titles. This conflict leads to the question of whether a sports governance model would be achievable in esports, with the need for more research on the matter.

Chapter 2: Research Question and Methodology

2.1 Research Question and Objectives

The aim of this research is to compare and evaluate existing and past governance models, case law and events within Esports and Sport to understand how Esports can develop a system to better protect its stakeholders. To achieve the aim, the research will have three objectives, which are:

- To examine past and existing governance models within esports (WESA, ESIC, KeSPA, etc.) in their effectiveness to deal with legal challenges and stakeholders' issues.
- To understand how current and future issues facing esports regulation may be addressed by governance.
- To understand if sports law may be adopted or adapted to better protect the integrity and governance of esports and its key stakeholders (Players, Teams and Tournament Organisers).

2.2 Methodology

Before the collection of data ethical approval (UCFBREC20W058) was given in which implications in the research such as search bias and flagging suspected plagiarism was considered (Appendix A). The methodology for this research project will be a review of the literature to ensure that the research questions is answered effectively. Using this method allows for “the building of research and relating it to existing knowledge” this will then allow for the “generating of new ideas and directions of a particular field” (Snyder, 2019). The purpose of the research is to understand the different governance models and organisations that have developed within esports and sport as a result of cases, events and past models. A review of the literature would be best suited to this study as the core data being based on case law and existing literature would provide the depth of data required to effectively answer the research question (Appendix B). Academics that have reviewed this methodology stated that it allows for a more beneficial and constructive view on cultural context and analyses within legal research (Little, 2005; Baude, *et al*, 2016).

A systematic review as defined by Uman (2011) is “a detailed and comprehensive plan and search strategy, with the goal of reducing bias by identifying, appraising, and synthesising all relevant studies on a particular topic”. This design allows for

researchers to filter and locate data and literature, to give reliable and accurate data to answer the research questions effectively. It then allows the researcher to analyse and interpret data or literature in a similar or different way past researchers may not have considered or due to future data has allowed for further analysis. The additional benefit of a focus of secondary data through a systematic review is that it enables “a more rigorous demonstration of evidence that makes it easier for readers to evaluate whether the ultimate claims are true or false” (Baude, *et al*, 2016). With a high degree of evidence, it enables for a more comprehensive approach to understanding legal and governance issues within esports.

For the research project, the data analysis method chosen was thematic analysis following the method laid out by Braun and Clarke (2013). The analysis was conducted in four steps familiarisation, generating initial codes, generating and reviewing themes and refining themes. The first step of familiarisation was to filter and highlight potential items of interest with relevance to the research question. The second part was to review this data and provide a label to describe the data to ensure a smooth process to develop themes. The next step involved reviewing the data and identifying what areas overlapped between codes to generate a theme that was of relevance. The final stage was to review the themes if they worked with the data collected, this led to some of the themes being filtered further and some being removed entirely.

Chapter 3: The Standardisation and Evolution of Governance in Sport

3.1 Background of Governance in Sport

Sport has been a part of society for centuries and can be traced back 3000 years ago to the start of the Olympics in Greece, it has grown in popularity and within the last few centuries has become a commercial product. Governance organisations started to form in the 18th and 19th century with organisations such as the MCC for cricket and The Football Association being the most notable setting out a list of rules for which the sport should be played (The FA, 2020). These sporting organisations around the world continued to evolve in line with the times and the rising commercialisation of sports. This chapter will look at how sports governance structures have formed over time, good and bad governance and the key principles that have been established for sports governance to operate effectively. With sports and esports having a similar structured ecosystem looking at the lessons from sports long history would enable esports to avoid mistakes made by sports in the past.

Sports governance can occur on multiple levels from local to international, as they exercise power with consideration given to influence, authority and the nature of decision making (Parent, M., 2016). In the Olympic charter, further clarifies the purpose of sports governance and can be applied to any sport stating “Freely establishing and controlling the rules of sports, determining the structure and governance of their organisations, enjoying the right of elections free from any outside influence and the responsibility for ensuring the principles of good governance is applied” (Olympic, 2020). These sports organisations all exist with a purpose and it is essential for these organisations to work towards efficiency and effectiveness, which are highlighted within their mission and vision statements (Sports Governance Academy, 2021). As sports organisations have grown with increased participants, funding and commercialisation, it has been important that they continue to evolve in key areas such as structure, while demonstrating good governance to keep the focus on their mission and vision for sport entails.

There are three components that contribute to a good structure of a sports organisation (Nikolaidou, S. *et al*, 2015); Formalisation is the extent that formal, rules and procedures are used by the organisation; Complexity refers to the number of levels that the organisation has should this be horizontal or vertical; Centralisation can be

either centralised where decisions are made at the top or decentralised where decisions are made throughout the organisation. As the organisation grows, they will have to become more formalised and complex to accommodate additional challenges and responsibilities. Failure to adapt the organisation would become bureaucratic and a lack of adherence to rules, slow decision making, and miscommunication will appear (Sports Governance Academy, 2021). In Europe, governance usually follows a pyramid structure, where National Governing Bodies sit at the top nationally with regional bodies in place, with grassroots organisations sitting at the bottom. The national organisations are not autonomous as there are further organisations above them at European and International levels. To ensure that governing bodies have authority, participants are required to only participate in competitions sanctioned by the NGB (De Marco, N., 2018).

3.2 The Evolution of Governance in Sport

Governance organisations have had to go through a lot of evolution to understand what the best principles are to achieve good governance. This has mostly come from external challenges from executive and legislative powers as well as public scrutiny to invoke change. In the UK, the House of Commons presented the 1968 Chester Report (Dr Chester, N., 1968), which looked at the governance of the FA and how it should progress in the future stating that it should be streamlined by having fewer FA members. The FA members failed to pass this recommendation as it would have voted them out of existence, this showed organisations have always been less willing to give up power to provide better governance (Wigmore, T., 2017). It has not only been NGB's that have shown poor governance but also International Sports Federations most notably FIFA and the IOC with reports and convictions of corruption over the last couple of decades. In 1999, the IOC found that six members had violated the bidding process for the 2002 Winter Games by taking bribes of thousands of dollars, they were later expelled from the IOC but has been found not to have broken "any laws" (Siddons, L., 1999). FIFA also had similar circumstances where multiple members and president Sepp Blatter had taken bribes in relation to TV rights being sold, referee decisions and bidding processes for international competitions (BBC, 2015). These arrests ultimately led to doubt of the transparency and process of the bidding process as well as the overall structure of the organisation (Forster, J., 2016).

These events have underlined key principles that organisations should implement to ensure good governance takes place. Most recently Sport England brought forward reforms to the way in which they issue funding by laying out several principles that organisations must have within its governance to get public funding, this would affect organisations such as the FA and ECB (Sports England, 2017). The three key principles introduced are transparency, accountability and financial integrity (The FA, 2016). Previous events and existing principles laid out by academics and organisations can help esports avoid mistakes that sports organisations have made in relation to governance and avoid unnecessary growing pains that the sports industry had during its commercialisation period. With esports and sports sharing many similarities it shows that esports should learn from the governance issues sports has faced and instantly ensure the correct principles are implemented with their governance structures.

Chapter 4: Esports and Sport “The Right to Govern”

4.1 Sports “The Right to Govern”

Publishers spend thousands and millions on game development in the process of developing, marketing and releasing the game to the general public, this means the publishers have the overall control of the game. Publishers can control any aspect of the game from the mechanics within the game to the rules of how to play it or what they can play it on as they control the intellectual property. This is very much unlike sport in which Governing Bodies do not have a specific right to govern and cannot stop rival governing bodies from being established (James, 2017, p.32). This has previously been seen within darts in 1992 with a group of players splitting from the British Darts Organisation (BDO) to establish the Professional Darts Corporation (PDC). The PDC saw itself as a professional organisation while BDO was for all levels of sport which ultimately saw it being recognised as the NGB for darts in the UK in 2005. In the case of *R v Football Association Ltd ex p Football League Ltd* [1993], it showed there is little that can be done to stop members leaving and establishing a new governing body or even an adapted sport.

4.2 Esports “The Right to Govern”

With publishers having full control of how their game can be used it makes them the top authority when regulating how their game is used within the esports industry. There are two common ways in which publishers approach the governing of their esports titles through a Top-heavy (Franchise) or Community/Licensee approach (Figure 1). A top-heavy approach sees the publishers have more direct contact with professional leagues and tournaments, this commonly sees the publisher run their own leagues and commonly see franchise leagues in place as seen within League of Legends and Call of Duty. With more direct control it means that the publisher has more control over the rules and regulations of the leagues and creates an economic system within the esports scene by filtering more funds into lower-level leagues. Using Riot’s League of Legends model, it sees them control the highest level of competitive play (LEC, LCS, etc), and then this is filtered into an academy system which is franchised in North America, but is licenced to Dreamhack for European Competition. This ultimately allows Riot to dictate the esports scene that establishes a consistent set of rules and route for players and teams to follow to progress within the ranking system.

The other approach publishers take is a Licensee/Community approach, which is a more relaxed approach to who and how tournaments/leagues are run. Licensing agreements are used by publishers to ensure that tournament organisers and competitive platforms are in line with the interest and aims of the publisher for the esports title. Things that can be seen within a license agreement can be what sponsors are prohibited to be associated with the game such as alcohol, drugs or tobacco or the ban of specific words or phrases in the chat function on the broadcast (Blizzard, 2020). License applications are becoming more common in esports as seen with Activision's rejection of an application from 100 Thieves to use the Call of Duty Warzone for their charity tournament. The charity tournament was supported by CashApp that fully funded the running of the tournament, however, Activision would only grant permission for the use of the game if CashApp was removed as a sponsor (Bernal, 2020). It was reported that Activision felt the sponsors involved could hinder future sponsorship of the game mode in the future.

An example of a Licensee/Community approach can be seen with Valve's Counter-Strike Global Offensive, one of the longest standing esports franchises since its first release in 1999. The only direct control that Valve has is through their Major competition that occurs twice a year through open qualifiers. This is in collaboration with a tournament organiser (ESL, Dreamhack, Faceit, etc.) that go through a bidding process to secure the rights. This means that any rulings that Valve has made on a competitive play such as not allowing coaches in-game to player bans are in effect for these tournaments (Valve Corp. CSGO, 2015). For other events to occur tournament organisers must obtain a license, these have meant more tournaments and leagues are widely available for teams and players to participate throughout the year compared to franchised esports titles. While a licensing approach has meant more organisers being involved, it has enabled the publishers to spend fewer resources on the development of the esports ecosystem of the game. It has further led to organisers to improve its structure of leagues/tournaments while also improving broadcasting standards to challenge other organisers. While having multiple organisers operate in one esports title it has seen the creation of bodies such as WESA and ESIC to investigate and highlight key discrepancies with the esports scene (WESA, 2019). The reason for more regulation bodies being created is due to the hands-off approach that occurs through a licencing system from publishers. This has ensured that there is more

accessible procedure for disputes through arbitration for players, teams and organisers. For more community events for amateur semi-professional players platforms such as ESEA and Faceit use an integrated platform through Valve's client Steam that ensures that these platforms operate in line with the publishers loosened agreements that tournament organisers use.

Figure 1: Diagram of Publishers Approach to Governance

Chapter 5: Early Governance in Esports

Publishers have not always been involved in esports in the early days of the industry between 1972 and 1999 tournaments would be held by students or local players with no recognised organiser (Larch, F., 2019). Over these years esports would grow with publishers taking more notice of competitive gaming with Nintendo holding the first 'Nintendo World Championships' in 1999. With the introduction of more multiplayer games being held over the internet esports grew with it becoming more accessible. With the industry growing, national governments started to take note and implemented governance organisations while others decided to create their own governance organisation with no government backing (Gewirtz, J, 2019). This chapter will look at if the early governance of esports was success or a failure, with government backed organisation and independent organisation.

5.1 KeSPA (Korean Esports Association)

The first governance organisation was formed in Korea as the Korea Esports Association (KeSPA), which was backed by South Korea's Ministry of Culture and Tourism. The purpose of this organisation was to promote game culture, regulate and organise esports competition in South Korea with the backing of the Government. Since its introduction in 2000, it has organised hundreds of competitions ranging in over 24 game titles (KeSPA, 2021). The KeSPA has had notable incidents over its duration the most severe being match-fixing and a lawsuit with Blizzard over IP rights.

In 2010, a series of posts created by professional players highlighted certain players within the KeSPA sanctioned league were matchfixing, benefiting from online betting platforms in Korea. This led to an investigation by KeSPA, the organisation found that 11 players were involved in fixing matches and immediately given lifetime bans from KeSPA competitions (Liquipedia.net, 2019). KeSPA also brought criminal charges against the players with the support of the Government and players were given suspended sentences and fines up to \$10,000 (News.BBC.co.uk, 2010). At the time these players were playing part-time, and the competitions were not large enough to warrant a prison sentence. Five years later at a stage where esports players were funded full-time, KeSPA had to release a statement that multiple players had been approached to match fix games and that they were working with authorities to solve the issue (Dailyesports.com, 2015). After a joint investigation from KeSPA and the

authorities in South Korea in 2016, two pro players Lee Seung-hyun and Jung Woo-yong were charged with matchfixing alongside 11 other brokers and financial backers. They were both permanently banned from KeSPA competitions, received an 18-month suspended sentence and a \$50,000 fine (Jung-hoon, L., 2016). These incidents of match-fixing highlight the benefit of having a governance model in place to provide regular regulation and review of betting activity surrounding its sanctioned matches, esports players and teams within South Korea (Chao, L. L., 2017). Also having the backing of the Government has allowed KeSPA to work with good authority and partnership to ensure that players going against Korean law are properly investigated and prosecuted.

KeSPA hasn't been without its problems, in 2007 KeSPA was given rights to broadcast Starcraft II tournaments from the publisher Blizzard. The issue, however, was that KeSPA then sold these broadcasting rights to two TV channels MBC Game and OnGameNet without the permission of Blizzard for three years paying \$258,000 (GamesIndustry.biz, 2010). In 2010, Blizzard and KeSPA cut ties due to the unapproved selling of broadcast rights from the organisation. Even after this, the two broadcasters continued to run tournaments despite not having secured IP rights from Blizzard. This led to Blizzard bringing forward litigation against KeSPA, MBC and OnGameNet, as a last resort to protect their IP rights. The claim from KeSPA was that "Blizzard collecting license fees for tournaments would be the equivalent to Adidas levying costs on its balls used in football matches" (Tong-hyung, K., 2010). This quote highlights a key difference between sport and esports as publishers have invested large amounts of money and resources to produce the game, compared to a sport that does not require specific software to play as it hasn't been developed by a singular company. Blizzard progressed with selling the broadcasting and operation rights to Gretch-GomTV as well as permission to sell rights to tv broadcasts (Leahy, 2010) with case against blizzard eventually being dropped after an agreed settlement. This case shows that due to copyright legislation, that governance organisations such as KeSPA will find it difficult to fully govern an esports title without the permission/backing of the publisher of the game even with backing from National Government.

5.2 British Esports

Other early esports governance organisations had other issues with governing esports on a national level as seen within the UK with the creation of the UKeSA in 2009. The organisation stated it was established to govern amateur and professional esports in the UK, that would build a unified structure of government, industry and community (Gameshell.com, 2009). The Chief Executive Ray Mia stated that the organisation was the beginning of what they would like to see as the gaming equivalent of The FA (Cadred.org, 2009). The organisation started to run national leagues across multiple esports with the support of large organisations such as Dell, Fnatic, Reason Gaming and Team Dignitas as well as hiring leading esports figures to head the Executive Committee. After the conclusion of season one, the UKeSA had filed for bankruptcy and had their assets taken, while teams and players were left without any payments for participation in the league (Lewis, R., 2009). The UKeSA collapsed due to the focus on the monetary gain from creating their own competitions, an opposite approach to the KeSPA that had licenced events with other broadcasters and organisations. Later in 2016, the British Esports Association (BEA) was formed under the authority of the UK Government under the Department of Media, Culture and Sport. This new organisation would focus on the “grassroots” community, with an enhanced focus on the use of esports in schools and colleges across the country (British Esports, 2021). The BEA does however state that it does not operate as a governing body like the KeSPA. The chairman of the BEA advisory board explained that the body “does not want to get involved with regulator issues as they are set by the publishers and that’s it” (MCVUK, 2017).

Chapter 6: The Evolution of Governance in Esports

With massive increases in revenue and viewership meant stakeholders wanted more security over the integrity of the game and the structure outside in the form of tournament organisers. Over 2016, it saw the introduction of two governance organisations in the form of the World Esports Association (WESA) and Esports Integrity Commission (ESIC). The creation of these organisations were backed by several major stakeholders within the esports ecosystem such as ESL and Dreamhack. Both organisations were created with a different purpose on how they operate and govern their effective area of esports. WESA was created to oversee the further “professionalization of esports through the introduction of player representation, standardization regulations and revenue sharing for teams” (WESA, 2016). ESIC would focus on the integrity of esports competition by “prevention, investigation and prosecution of all forms of cheating, including, but not limited to, match manipulation and doping” (ESIC, 2020). This chapter will look at the new emerging governance organisations actions that have impacted stakeholders and if these organisations are improving governance standards in esports.

6.1 World Esports Association

WESA was formed with ESL which is one of the largest esports companies in the world most notably holding tournaments in multiple game titles such as CS:GO and DOTA 2. The formation of WESA also included eight esports teams (Fnatic, Natus Vincere, EnVyUs, Virtus.Pro, Faze, mousesports and NIP) alongside ESL, that has eventually grown to 14 teams joining the organisation as members (WESA, 2016). In the early months of the association, it saw one of its founding members Faze leave after a week of operation citing that WESA product was ‘halfway there’ and the lack of North American organisation being involved (Wolf, J., 2016). The issue raised concerns about the association as it meant that all member teams were based in Europe and lacked diversity of teams from other continents meaning that their concerns would not be dealt with. This highlights the potential bias of governing organisations that exists within esports against less profitable or popular regions that might to have bigger fanbases or commercial pull.

Over the years since its formation, it has shown effective governance and creating more professionalism in esports and within the CS:GO ecosystem. At the start of 2017

WESA's first move was selling the streaming rights of ESL CS:GO Pro League to YouTube and then in 2018 selling the ESL One and Pro League to Facebook (WESA, 2017). This prompted other tournament organisers such as ECS to also sell streaming rights of their competition to other platforms such as Twitch. WESA also introduced several comprehensive regulations, including Multi-Team ownership prohibition, a personal code of conduct and sanction regulations (WESA, 2017). This was a positive move by the association as many teams and fans were concerned about the conflict of interest of the Danish business RFRSH owning two teams Astralis and Heroic that were competing against each other in a number of esports competitions. WESA and RFRSH then announced an agreement that RFRSH would comply with the Multi-Team Ownership Regulations stating "RFRSH shares the same vision as WESA to further professionalize the esports industry" (WESA, 2017). The agreement allowed an 18-month grace period for RFRSH to comply with the regulation and this was resolved when they sold Heroic to Serenades Global Inc (Villanueva, J., 2018). This has shown that the authority and the importance of an organisation such as WESA is valued by teams to improve the esports ecosystem and shows that esports stakeholders want to follow the principle of transparency from sports.

WESA has not been without its controversies as one of the member teams (NIP) was subject to several claims from former staff and players about how the business was operated and how CEO Hicham Chahine led the operation (Lewis, R., 2019). WESA proceeded to open an independent investigation mandating ESIC Commissioner Mr Ian Smith to oversee the complainants and share the findings of the investigation publicly (Mira, L, 2019). As a part of the investigation, Mr Smith received full and unfettered access to NIP's documentation at their office, interviewed several shareholders current and former at length on a total of 18 public complaints and some private complaints against NIP (Smith, I., 2019). The key complaints are that a number of players/staff were owed money, the movement of funds from former management Oldco to new management Newco and that the company had misappropriated charity money from an account. The report was commissioned by WESA on the 21st of August 2019 and set a deadline of the 31st of August 2019 for the investigation to be submitted, this allowed a considerable short window for Mr Smith to conduct his investigation. This issue of the amount of time raised concerns amongst the community that it would not be an effective length of time to investigate all complaints.

Other issues with the short time frame are that there were close to 20,000 emails alongside other documents that Mr Smith had to review as well as translating each one from Swedish using Google Translate (Smith, I., 2019). Mr Smith stated in his report he could not read all of them but looked at as many as he could that “was important threads”, he also stated that things may be lost in translation due to the use of Google Translate. The short timeline to submit the findings shows that there were sacrifices that the investigator had to take such as getting a translation and being able to take his time to review all available documents. The process of this investigation has shown a weakness in how WESA operates in not allowing for a transparent and thorough process due to not disclosing if Hicham Chahine was involved in the selection of investigator.

Another issue that arose was from other team owners external to WESA about if a conflict of interest was involved in the report and if it was truly independent to WESA. One vocal owner of Ence Esports Tomi Kovanen stated it was “shocking, and worrying for implications on how WESA conducts the rest of its business, that they think not using an outside counsel is absolutely necessary for what amounts to an internal investigation” (Steven, R., 2019). The issues Mr Kovanen highlighted were WESA financial ties with ESIC in which Mr Smith is the commissioner of, as WESA pays ESIC to review and investigate any integrity issues within their competitions such as ESEA League and Pro League. The second issue raised was the board that appointed Mr Smith as the investigator had at the time Mr Hicham Chahine CEO of NIP and primary shareholder sitting on the board. This created confusion as to whether he had input on the appointment on who investigated the claims made against NIP, WESA did not respond to this claim so it is unsure how much influence he had on the appointment. This issue draws comparisons to the case of Gundel (1993) that saw the horse rider appeal the CAS decision to the Swiss Federal Tribunal over not meeting the conditions of impartiality and independence required by CAS. The outcome ultimately meant that CAS had to go through a reform in 1994 to ensure these conditions are met to be considered a proper arbitration court.

While the immediate decision of WESA to investigate the claims made against one of the member teams showed clear action of governance to protect the integrity of the association, the highlighted issues meant that stakeholders were concerned about

how it was conducted. Since the investigation, WESA has not had to issue another investigation on any matters, but after vocal claims from stakeholders about the process the association will improve the process in which it is handled.

6.2 Esports Integrity Commission

ESIC is another governance organisation that deals with the integrity of esports compared to WESA that governs the competition of esports. Competition organisers such as ESL, Blast Series and Dreamhack pay a financial fee for the organisation to investigate and review integrity issues within esports competition. ESIC also works with betting companies to help identify match-fixing and other issues related to betting in esports. Formed in 2016, it has handled and investigated some of the most controversial issues of integrity within esports. The organisation prides itself on bringing the sport process over to esports to provide a fair process of justice, implementation of standards and recognition of sanctions (ESIC, 2020). After its creation in 2016, it announced its disciplinary panel made up of eight members that come from sports law, esports law and esports operational backgrounds chaired by Kevin Carpenter (ESIC, 2017). This panel would hear several cases mostly on appeals of handed bans from ESIC, in which the panel can be truly independent of ESIC to ensure there is no conflict of interest or bias. Early in the operation of ESIC dealt with a number of small issues such as cheating bans in smaller tournaments such as the five-year ban of Nikhil “Forsaken” Kumawat for cheating at the ESL India Premiership live finals for Optic India (ESIC, 2018). At the start of 2020 ESIC had now grown to accommodate several large members such as Blast Series, ESL, Dreamhack, UCC, Betway, Loot.box and Unikrn (ESIC, 2021). With more financial backing due to an increase in members, it would mean the organisation would be able to put more resources into its investigation and operations.

In 2020 there were four main issues that ESIC were involved in that showed the successes and limitations of their operations, these were MDL Australia match-fixing, Godsent’s Provisional Ban, Stream Sniping in online play and Coach Bug Bans in CS:GO. Due to the outbreak of Covid-19 at the start of 2020 all esports competition were able to continue online instead of at LAN finals within arenas. This meant that it was possible for teams and players to watch the live stream of the game while playing to gain a competitive advantage over the other team also referred to as “Stream

Sniping”. ESIC stance on this was to investigate the issue and announced they would take a “Zero-tolerance” approach to stream sniping while suggesting a number of recommendations to organisers this included increasing stream delay to three minutes (Mira, L., 2020). ESIC stated that they had received several allegations of stream snipping behaviour during May and June of 2020 and further explained they had assessed compelling evidence that was alarming of how regularly it was used (ESIC, 2020). The organisation however would only charge two teams Cloud9 and Furia with the violation of stream sniping that resulted in fines for both teams (Lewis, J., 2020). This action questioned whether ESIC was implementing a “zero-tolerance” policy, but Ian Smith Commissioner of ESIC stated that the reason a “zero-tolerance” policy was not undertaken at first was that it would have done more harm than good and with the limited resources that it has it would have taken months to investigate all offences (Mira, L., 2020).

As a result of the stream sniping investigation, it was found that ESIC would hand a six-month ban to Godsent that would prohibit them from participating in any ESIC sanctioned events (Lewis, J., 2020). The allegation was that the team was able to find out how much damage occurred during the round, however, this statistic can be viewed due to it being implemented by the publisher on the scoreboard within the game. This led to Godsent urging ESIC to seek consultation over its findings, which ultimately led to the ban being rescinded (Lewis, J., 2020). This event highlights that without the proper knowledge or understanding of what features within the game it can potentially lead to unjustified bans and could lead to the limiting ability of the organisation to address competitive integrity. ESIC stated that the error within the investigation was the result of inaccurate information from external ‘experts’ that ESIC uses (Lewis, J., 2020).

Later in 2020 ESIC issued seven players from the Australian ESEA MDL 12 month bans for placing bets through sites such as Betway on MDL and other CS:GO games which breached ESEA rules and Article 2.2 of ESIC’s Anti-corruption code (ESIC, 2020). This was then followed by a further 35 players within the same league being banned for the same offence with punishments ranging from 12 months to 60 months and two increased bans for previous parties (ESIC, 2021). This was the largest investigation that ESIC has conducted in relation to betting offences. This case shows

how ESIC can effectively work with anti-corruption partners such as Betway to identify activity that can affect the integrity of the competition. There has been vocal opposition about the process from the banned players claiming that they were not informed about the charges until the announcement of the bans were published by ESIC publicly (Mays, J., 2020). Under ESIC's Anti-Corruption Code that the betting and match-fixing bans fall under it states under Article 4.6 that the participant shall be sent a "Notice of Charge" when ESIC determines that there is a case to answer under Article 2 (Betting and Match Fixing Charges included) (ESIC, 2021). Straying away from their own procedures could be a dangerous precedent as it could leave players questioning if the bans should be upheld or made void. It also highlights that ESIC needs further evolution to ensure it follows its own procedures, to create more certainty for athletes and teams with its decisions.

In the later part of 2020 ESIC started an investigation into a new exploitation of a bug in CS:GO that allowed team coaches to freely view parts of the game during a round to get immediate information about the other player's positions. ESIC handed three bans under Article 2.3.3 of ESIC Code of Conduct "Cheating in an attempt to win a game or match" to Ricardo Sinigaglia (6 months), Nicolai Petersen (12 months) and Aleksandr Bogatyrev (24 months), this was prolific as two of these coaches had been a part of top ten ranked teams (ESIC, 2020). These initial bans triggered a further investigation into the bug that ESIC highlighted that they would have to review 25,000 matches and after reviewing 20% they had found a further 37 offending parties in which they were handed bans (ESIC, 2020). After this case, it also resulted in the first public release appeal from ESIC that Sergey 'LMBT' Bezhanov, had his ban rescinded after there was compelling evidence supplied that he was not at his computer and once informed of the bug had informed the admin (ESIC, 2020). The process of this case highlights how ESIC can protect the integrity of esports competition effectively and allow for an appeal process to occur fairly. This further proved with the backing of the bans from the publisher of the game Valve, establishing that any coaches banned through ESIC would also not be able to take part in Valve's sponsored major events depending on the ESIC demerits that occurred (Valve Corp. CSGO, 2021). This was also the first time that the publisher had awarded a ban through evidence or an investigation conducted by an external organisation, highlighting that publishers are open to working with external governance to protect the integrity of the competition.

ESIC has shown that it is a strong pillar of governance within esports, ensuring proper investigation into integrity issues within the competition and improving the level of professionalism within esports with proper avenues of process and appeal. However, issues still remain about how ESIC has conducted some of its process in line with its own code and the limited knowledge about specific games that could lead to discrepancies within its bans. These controversies over the handling of cases by ESIC can be linked to the lack of funding it received through its membership model, which receives no funding from publishers such as Valve. ESIC in 2020 operated on a budget of £250,000, an underwhelming amount compared to the ICC's budget of £2,000,000 that has a much lower reported caseload (HLTV org, 2020). With further funding and support, ESIC would be able to function on a more efficient level and discrepancies that have been discussed could be avoided.

6.3 Continental/Global Governance in Esports

While WESA is called a world esports association it operates in a very small region and specific circumstances such as competition and regions. There are three organisations that operate or deal with continental or global governance, these are Esports Europe, Global Esports Federation (GEF) and International Esports Federation (IESF). Each involves different members, different ideas and objectives to which they believe governance should be achieved within esports.

6.3.1 International Esports Federation (IESF)

The oldest global esports organisation is the International Esports Federation (IESF), established in 2008 with nine associations from Denmark, South Korea, Germany, Austria, Belgium, Netherlands, Switzerland, Vietnam and Taiwan. They highlighted four principles that the organisation will pursue: increasing membership, global standardisation, education and hosting the world championship (International Esports Federation, 2020). They have since increased their members to 98 national associations with the majority coming from Asia (International Esports Federation, 2020). The IESF has highlighted the structure of KeSPA and the way it is run as the precedent that associations should take when governing nationally, however, association members all take different approaches while maintaining the minimum required by the IESF (International Esports Federation, 2020). An issue of the IESF is

that technically any organisation can be recognised as the national esports organisation if they pay a fee to the federations and implement basic regulations laid out. This was seen with the inclusion of the United eSports Federation (USEF), which the IESF recognised as the national governing body of esports in the US (Mackay, D., 2018). Since the recognition of the USEF it has stated that it planned to unite all esports stakeholders from athletes to IP holders. In the three years of operations since its acceptance in 2018, the operations it entails is holding online events and running a national team to compete at IESF tournaments (Esports Federation, 2018). It highlighted that with a payment of the membership fee that any group of people could try to gain recognition from the IESF as a governing body within a country.

6.3.2 Global Esports Federation (GEF)

The newest global organisation to join with the aim of esports governance is the Global Esports Federation formed in 2019 with the objectives; encouraging and supporting standards, guidelines and regulations of esports, establishing athlete welfare, develop governance structures and to create a Global Esports Games (Global Esports, 2020). While the GEF and IESF are similar in what they want to achieve with esports governance, GEF are backed by Tencent as their founding global partner (Global Esports, 2020). This is significant as Tencent is one of the largest companies in the world and owns Riot Games and Epic Games as well as minority stakes in Ubisoft and Activision Blizzard. These developers own major esports titles such as League of Legends, Overwatch, Fortnite and Call of Duty (Frank, A., 2015). This allows the governance body to get backing from publishers about specific regulation and rules involving competitions within a specific game, something that IESF does not possess in its partnerships. This gives more authority to the approach that GEF can take in establishing its objectives for governing esports. A slight concern is that with a large stake in the majority of esports titles Tencent could potentially use its influence to affect other publishers with a large esports base such as Valve. There are concerns about conflict of interest due to Tencent having ownership of esports brands and teams that could potentially compete in GEF sanctioned events (Zhao, Y. & Lin, Z., 2020).

There were also concerns about the formation of the board that would head the Global Esports Federation and the purpose of a global games. The board of GEF is formed of one president and three vice-presidents, with the unclear procedure of how they are

elected and the amount of control they have. All the board come from a traditional sports background with all being involved in international or national Olympic associations (Liang, J-H., 2019). Having an experienced board of Olympic background highlights the ambitions of the GEF to maybe push for esports to be within the Olympics or to try and make their global games an esports alternative to the Olympics. It does however highlight a lack of experience within esports and raises questions as to whether they can help with the other objectives including rules of competition and player welfare. Within esports, there has been a history of international esports competition notably from Alibaba that created the World Electronic Sports Games, another being the World Cyber Games and the IESF's World Championship. There has not been a shortage of companies and governing organisations trying to make an "Olympic" style event for each country to have a team represented in each esports title, but it has historically had bad reviews (Abdul Aziz, S., 2019). In the past these competitions have failed to pay teams prize money and players have not seen the purpose with an already flooded schedule of tournaments and that most esports teams involve several nationalities in the roster. This illustrates that the majority of these organisations are targeting profit through these "Olympic style" competitions than looking to improve the governance on a global level.

Chapter 7: The Next Step for Esports Governance

This chapter will look at what academics suggest is the best path for esports to take to improve governance with the recommendation of continued use of esports organisations such as WESA to a restructured model similar to FIFA. The chapter will also examine if these suggestions alongside the analysis from previous chapters would be beneficial to implement into the esports ecosystem to benefit stakeholders. The four suggestions are to establish an international esports association with federal backing at a national level (Chao, 2017), the implementation of an e-FIFA organisation with an umbrella structure with a regulatory body for each esports underneath (Martinelli, J., 2019), the creation of a Network Administration Organisation (NAO) model (Peng *et al*, 2020) and the continued use of existing esports organisations with more publisher responsibility (Bouet & Rønn, 2018).

7.1 International Esports Association and National Governing Bodies

Chao (2017) suggests having an international esports association that then puts pressure on national governments to provide funding in the form of national governing bodies. The research highlights that having an international esports association would increase uniformity, sporting ethics and standardisation, which is seen with sporting associations such as the Olympic association. The author also highlights that if an IEA was to start effectively regulating and governing esports it would put pressure on federal action to implement government backed NGB's. This has been shown within the cases of the UKeSA collapse and KeSPA v Blizzard (2010) that saw NGB's in esports require national government backing to be effective, it would also support the rise of national competitions such as ESL National Leagues and UKLC. The French Government in 2016 showed how important it is for national government powers to be involved in esports at a national level by implementing minimum standards for player contracts, visa issues and rights for minors under 16 (Znaty, B., 2017). The legislation passed ensured there was better protection of player rights that publishers could not issue due to the different legal process in each country.

However, as examined in chapter 6 international esports associations such as IeSF and GEF have not been well received by stakeholders due to the creation of multiple organisations leading to confusion and issues related to the operation and funding. IEA also lacks authority due to not having the backing of publishers as they own the

IP rights and the GEF is only IEA with publishers backing but involves a conflict of interest through Tencent ownership. Around the world, some Governments are also sceptical of its involvement in esports. In the UK the DCMS provides funding to non-profits such as the BEA and UKIE that are involved in Esports. The DCMS has recognised esports as a key industry within the economy and has put forward proposals on loot boxes and athlete visas, but have been reluctant to be involved in further governance of esports (Sacco, D., 2020).

7.2 A FIFA Model

The second suggestion from Martinelli (2019) is to implement an e-FIFA model with a head authority sitting at the top then organisations under the umbrella to govern the different esports with provided a standardisation across all esports. The researcher highlights two key reasons for a FIFA model to govern esports is the “following of Swiss law” and “utilising CAS to tackle legitimacy concerns”. By following Swiss law, it would enable to remove confusion and enforcement issues within esports as well as creating a clear direction for esports to follow. A global organisation that governs a standard across all publishers would also ensure bans can be transferred as seen in the *Olkkonen v Valve Corp* (2020) case that an athlete moves from one esports title to another avoiding a ban from the major competition (Rawat, A., 2020). The FIFA model of having individual organisations govern specific esports titles would also ensure that publishers do not lose all control of how their esports entity is run.

There are issues however with the suggestion as some publishers have openly stated that they prioritise creating games rather than an esports company (Smith, 2020). This comment from Ian Smith highlights why as stated in Chapter 3, that publishers like Valve use a licensee approach to commission who can use its property rights for esports purposes. It means it would be difficult for all publishers to agree on how they govern esports as well as how much wait one publisher has over another as games go in and out of fashion with consumers. Companies like Tencent that own several publishers have also already started their own governance organisation in the form of Global Esports Federation. It shows that publishers are aware of their responsibility to govern esports but with more individual federations there is a smaller chance of a collective effort.

7.3 Network Administration Organisation (NAO)

Peng (2020) takes a similar approach to Martinelli (2019) highlighting that publishers need to take an authoritative approach to governance in esports, but Peng states that a Network Administration Organisation (NAO) model would be better suited. An NAO model incorporates publishers as the main players in the network as they hold IP rights, but states that emerging stakeholders such as local governments, teams, competition organisers should also be included in the governance structure. Having not only publishers govern the esports by stakeholders it would enable for a more collective approach and ensure that regional and global voices are heard, which has been neglected at a grassroots level. The issue with an NAO model is reliant on the need for publishers in the network and without it would be limited in its power, as seen with IEA's such as IeSF in the past. The research does highlight that the model would not suit the current climate in esports and would require more economic growth for some publishers to take more responsibility for their governing responsibilities. The growth of esports would also create "blind spots" such as matchfixing, cheating and agent regulations that only a collective response from publishers would be required to deal with issues.

7.4 The Continuation of Existing Governance Organisations

The final suggestion is from Bouet & Rønn (2018) that takes a more short-term approach with how to deal with governance in esports by suggesting that publishers take more responsibility and for existing governance organisations to improve its standards. The research highlighted that WESA has been improving the professionalism of esports with the introduction of an athletic council and removing a degree of conflict of interest, but players thought it was not transparent and was not truly independent of ESL. It also reviewed ESIC and the IeSF stating they followed the same line as WESA with not being independent enough and could "not significantly improve the current governance situation in esports" (Bouet & Rønn, 2018). As a result, it believed that publishers need to take more responsibility as they held the IP rights of the games, as they could eliminate uncertainties to a high degree. An issue of this suggestion is that if the publisher takes varied stances on different games it could create an undesirable environment for some stakeholders as it could restrict some of their operations.

7.5 The Best Direction for Esports Governance

At its current stage, the recommendation from Bouet & Rønn (2018) is the most suitable in the short-term, ultimately the publishers have the highest power to govern its selective game because of IP rights. Esports is at a stage where individual esports face different issues that require publisher intervention, these have been partially addressed by organisations such as ESIC. However, ESIC faces their own issues with funding and resources available to cover all integrity issues. By having more responsibility from publishers, it would create a lot more certainty for a range of stakeholders and remove elements of confusion. If selective publishers continue to take a backseat when governing esports, it will require existing organisations ESIC and WESA to improve their current practices. They would need to better improve on existing principles highlighted in sports such as transparency, accountability and financial integrity. Transparency is a key element that both organisations need to improve, as highlighted in chapter 6 both have had complaints that there is no clear communication between them and stakeholders. National and grassroots competition has also become a lot bigger and would require the creation of national governing bodies with the backing of executive powers. With executive backing, it would ensure that the failure of past self-established NGB's such as the UKeSA does not reoccur. It would also enable a more collective approach nationally as well as create a degree of standardisation and professionalisation, something that has been seen since the creation of KeSPA in South Korea.

This short-term vision would only hinder the governance of esports due to the expected growth of the industry; more businesses will enter the space from teams to event organisers. As the industry grows the integrity of competition and legal disputes around a range of issues will grow in correlation meaning the existing structures in esports will be unable to keep up with the growing demand. It will ultimately lead to the need for a unified body with publishers as highlighted by Peng (2020) to cover these "blind spots", so an NAO governance model would be better implemented in the future. With esports expected to continue to grow as an industry, it is ever more important for publishers to take a collective approach sooner rather than later to ensure esports reputation and growth is not tarnished by governance issues (Nordland, J., 2021).

Chapter 8: Conclusion

As esports continues to grow as an industry there will be significant pressure on the governance and integrity of esports affecting stakeholders. The aim of this research was to examine existing and past governance models and cases within both sport and esports to determine how esports could better protect its stakeholders. Sports draws a lot of comparisons to esports and has gone through its own governance restructures and investigations to better protect the industry and integrity of sports. Sports governance is still evolving but has learnt from incidents over the years including corruption in FIFA and the IOC that principles such as transparency, accountability and financial integrity are crucial in governing. Esports has grown at a rapid pace compared to sports and publishers have been at the front of the discussion of governance with each taking a different approach but due to IP rights ultimately have full power to govern. This has been shown with past and current governance organisations such as KeSPA, UKeSA, IeSF and EEF as they have struggled to stamp their authority without backing from publishers. Alongside this the continued creation of international esports organisations to be the proclaimed “the true global body for esports” has created much confusion for stakeholders about their authority and role within the industry. With the creation of WESA and ESIC, there have been glimpses of good governance existing in esports, with more being done from these organisations to take the integrity within competition. Even with numerous accounts of how they can improve the governance of esports, they have failed to implement two key principles of transparency and true independence.

There has been a common consensus about two points; that governance within esports needs to improve as it grows and that publishers are the most important factor for this to occur. Publishers control the intellectual property rights to the games that enable them to control the elements in the game and which tournaments organisers can use the game through a licensing scheme. In the short-term publishers will need to take more control over the governance of their specific games to create a level of professionalism and certainty for stakeholders. It is also important as grassroots competition becomes more popular that national governing bodies are set up with the backing of executive powers as seen within South Korea with the creation of the KeSPA. As the industry is expected to grow further it will require a collaborative effort from all publishers to work together to tackle “blind spots” that only collective effort can

fix. It will be difficult to achieve as most publishers have a different approach to how they govern their games with some more hands-on than others, but to keep esports sustainable and to improve the environment for stakeholders it will be crucial for a collaborative approach.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Ethics Approval

UCFB

UCFB Research Proposal Form for Secondary Data

1. **Signature of supervisor:** Alexander Chrysanthou **Date:** 14th October 2020

** Please note that ethical application will be immediately rejected if not approved with signature of supervisor*

2. **Personal Details**

Title	Mr	Forename	Sam	Surname	Wickham
E-mail: 21715908@ucfbstudent.com					

3. **Full Title of Project**

Adoption of Sports Law Principles in Esports: The need for a more comprehensive governance model in Esports to protect stakeholders.

4. **Justification of the research**

- explain the rationale for carrying out this project.
- Please include any review of relevant literature that supports the research; some academic underpinning should be provided to justify conducting the research

Due to the rapid growth of Esports over the last 10 to 20 years, it has led to the change of the landscape of competitive games and regulation of competitions. Within the journal article by Reitman, et al., (2019), it highlighted that there was a lack of research being conducted in seven key areas within Esports (Media Studies, Informatics, Business, Sport Science, Sociology, Law and Cognitive Science) with only 150 publications across all seven areas. It stated that "Esports research's nascency means there are still fundamental questions about how the field is unfolding" (Reitman, et al., 2019, p.49). This is a worrying trend developing around the research of Esports considering that it is projected to be an industry worth billions of dollars by 2023 (Soto Reyes, 2019).

With the continued classification of esports as a sport around the world, it would ultimately bring more litigation from and against a number of stakeholders in the industry (Kaburakis, et al. 2017). Within existing literature, there has been an evaluation of how esports governance and ecosystem could be subject to litigation. It

is only until recently in which more legal cases such as McLeod v. Valve Corporation (2016) and Okkonen v. Valve GmbH (2020), have highlighted the rapid growth of litigation against developers (Governing Bodies) over actions it has taken. The purpose of this project is to compare and evaluate existing and past governance models, case law and events within both Sport and Esports to understand how Esports can develop a system better to protect its stakeholders. By looking at a similar model and pathway to Esports it would enable a better understanding of what obstacles have occurred in the past and how these were tackled in sports.

5. **Aims and Research question**

- Outline the aim of the study and the research question under investigation
- If appropriate, outline the study hypotheses

Research Aim
 The primary aim of this research is to compare and evaluate existing and past governance models, case law and events within Esports and Sport to understand how Esports can develop a system to better protect its stakeholders.

Research Objectives

1. To examine past and existing governance models within Esports (WESA, LCS, KeSPA, etc) in its effectiveness to deal with legal challenges and stakeholder issues.
2. To understand how current and future issues facing Esports regulation may be tackled by governance.
3. To understand if Sports law may be adopted or adapted to better protect the integrity of esports and financial stability of key stakeholders (Players, Teams and 3rd Party Tournament Organisers).

6. **Research Methodologies**

- Please indicate the design(s) and other features of your study in relation to QUAL and QUANT methodologies

<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>Qualitative <u>Systematic Review Design</u> In Uman (2011) systematic review is defined as 'involving a detailed and comprehensive plan and search strategy, with the goal of reducing bias by identifying, appraising, and synthesizing all relevant studies on a particular topic.'. This way of design allows researchers to</p>
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filter and locate data and literature, to give reliable and accurate data to answer the research question effectively. This then allows the researcher to analyse and interpret data or literature in a similar or different way that past researchers may not have considered or due to future research has allowed for further analysis. With the research question being based around an established governance model and emerging governance model, reviewing past literature on sports governance would give a good foundation for answering the research aims. Systematic review does not also limit research to past published academic literature, it will also the extraction of data to also focus on law reviews and legal cases that have been published as well as published arbitration decisions within sport (CAS) and esports. This would allow for research on an emerging industry such as esports to collect data for a better comparison against an established industry such as sport.

7. Data Sources & Implications

- Indicate the sources you will use to gather secondary data from and whether there are any ethical implications involved.
- Please note that it is not acceptable to simply state that there are no ethical implications due to the data being secondary/publically available

The secondary data gathered to answer the research question will look at a range of available resources such as journal articles, law reviews, case law, published documents from esports and sports organisations, industry reports and articles from established news outlets in the industry.

Search Bias

It will be important to consider different types of bias when searching for literature such as multiple publication bias, language bias and database bias. Having preferences for certain studies with a large sample size are more likely to gain higher results on databases or search platforms (Suri, 2019). With the inclusion of grey

literature within the search of literature stage of the research process it will minimise the impact of certain biases.

Flagging Suspected Plagiarism

With the amount of literature that is consumed during a systematic review, it is important to be aware of potential plagiarisms within work, such as republication of an article under a different author. It is therefore important to alert both publishers to the similarities between the work and for it to be investigated (Wager & Wiffen, 2011). It should also be taken into consideration of who to reference if that piece of literature is to be used or is important within the systematic review.

Contributors Are Properly Acknowledged

When reflecting on other researcher's work such as academic publications it is important to avoid plagiarism. This means that efficient citations are important when reflecting or using other researcher's images, data or view/opinion on a topic or data set (Wager & Wiffen, 2011). To ensure that work is highlighted effectively to show another researcher's opinion/view, the use of quotation marks and citation will remove under certainty from the research.

8. **Data Collection Procedure**

- Describe the procedure that will be undertaken for collecting secondary data
- Provide enough information to ensure that the procedure can be replicated.

Secondary Data Collection Method

For the research that will be conducted it will focus on collecting secondary data through the use of systematic review. This method enables the use of existing academic literature from experienced academics and legal experts within sport and esports. It will also allow for the gathering of data through other avenues such as legal decisions within courts that are commonly seen within sports. A systematic review also enables data such as arbitration decisions and publisher/organisation announcements in regards to competition rules, due to the differential of publication in esports compared to existing sports.

A systematic review design has been cited by Baude, *et al* (2016) as a benefit within a legal-based research project or review as it enables "a more rigorous demonstration of evidence makes it easier for readers to evaluate whether the ultimate claims are true or false". This would be a significant benefit for this research project as due to the early adoption of esports within mainstream media and society, there are sceptics to its adoption of certain legal principles. With a high degree of evidence, it would enable readers to have a more comprehensive understanding of

the legal and governance issues within esports and its comparison to types of governance models in sport.

Inclusion Criteria:

In the data collection process a range of inclusion and exclusion criteria will be used to filter through the resources to gain and validate data which are suitable to use to answer the research question (Meline, 2006).

Criteria for Journals, Law Reviews and Case Law

- *Choice of Words:* A similar issue that has arisen in the literature review is the use of different words that describe competitive gaming with the more expected and the common word being esports. Within the search of the literature, it will be important to use the technique suggested by Creswell and Creswell (2018) to develop a list of keywords to ensure correct literature is obtained.
- *Location:* It will be a part of criteria that journals and law reviews would have had been based on either North American or European sport or esports to be included in the research. While case law must have taken place within a North American Court, European Court or EU Court.
- *Time Period:* Due to the research taking place will look at two different sectors it will be important to consider what time period the research should be conducted. For literature to be considered for this research it must have taken place after 1980 due to the commercial growth of the sport in this time period and the emergence of esports after this time period.
- *Peer-Review/Grey Literature:* Grey literature will also be considered within this systematic review as it is necessary to gain more data and context when answering the research question. Due to how internal arbitration is conducted within esports and sports certain decisions will be published through websites such as The F.A. or CAS, while esports decisions in arbitration are reported through either their website or trusted online news outlet. The inclusion of online news outlets reports within this systematic review could be considered to be a lower quality of data. However, due to the way in which some publishers such as Valve Corporation want to be transparent with fans it has seen scenarios where they favour popular community news platforms to release information. This has been recently seen with conflict of interest documents being released to a popular website within the esports community.

9. **Data Analysis Procedure**

- Describe the procedure that will be undertaken for analysing the data in your study
- Provide enough information to ensure that the procedure can be replicated.

Within this research project, the data analysis method chosen is a thematic analysis that will be conducted in four steps.

Step 1: Familiarisation

Once the data has been sourced the first step of the analysis will be to comb through and highlight potential items of interest. This will help identify content within the data relevant to the research question (Braun & Clarke, 2013)

Step 2: Generating Initial Codes

This step will be reviewing parts of the data and providing a label of what is relevant to the research question. The codes will give a summary or describe the data to ensure a smooth process to develop themes (Braun & Clarke, 2013).

Step 3: Generating and Review of Themes

This phase involves reviewing the code data to identify areas of similarity and overlaps between codes to generate a theme to highlight its relevance (Braun & Clarke, 2013).

Step 4: Refining Themes

This is a review of themes to ensure that they work in coordination of the data. This process may filter further or remove themes entirely (Braun & Clarke, 2013).

10. Reference List

- Cite up to 10 supporting references using Harvard Method

Baude, W., Chilton, A. & Malani, A. (2016) 'Making Doctrinal Work More Rigorous: Lessons from Systematic Reviews' *The University of Chicago Law Review*, 84(1), pp.37-58.

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11. Data Protection

Does your study involve the use of personal information?

(Personal information is information that can be used to identify the identity of an individual)

Yes

No

If so, have you complied with the requirements of UK Data Protection legislation? Please explain how you will meet these requirements?

Summary of Key Data Sources:

Collection of Journal Articles-

https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=esports+governance&og=

Arbitration Decisions ESIC-

<https://www.lawinsport.com/topics/sports/esports>

UK Case Decisions-

<https://www.bailii.org/>

UEFA Decisions-

<https://disciplinary.uefa.com/>

CAS Decisions-

<https://www.tas-cas.org/en/jurisprudence/recent-decisions.html>